

L: location of Sant'Omobono in Rome; R: site plan with trench D10 indicated in red.

The site of Sant'Omobono in Rome's Forum Boarium is crucial for understanding the development of human occupation of the urban area during the prehistoric and Archaic periods, as well as for the early monumentalization of its cult-places and their ongoing reëlaboration. The Sant'Omobono Project, a collaboration between the Sovrintendenza Capitolina ai Beni Culturali (Rome), the Università della Calabria (Cosenza), and the University of Michigan (Ann Arbor), began work on in 2009 (Brocato and Terrenato 2012; Brocato et al. 2012; Terrenato et al. 2012). In 2013, a deep trench, D10, was excavated directly south of the modern church.

Steel shoring for D10 blocking total station line-of-sight.

Because D10 was expected to reach a depth of X m below the level of the surrounding pavement and continue below the level of the water-table, it was necessary to install a system of steel shoring (the "box") to prevent collapse. The initial height of the sheeting presented practical problems for the project's usual procedures of topographic documentation, which rely on an electronic total station for depth measurement, requiring line of sight. The use of prism pole extensions to exceed the height of the sheeting was ruled out by the existence of a fixed sunshade over the top of the trench.

Openings between the four sides of the box provided the only possible sight-lines. However, the corners either did not allow for secure setup of a total station or were used for access to the trench, preventing a permanent total station setup. A sufficient and efficient methodology for documenting D10 was desired – sufficient, in that no more information should be lost than would be lost using a total station, and efficient, in that the documentation should neither unduly delay work in D10 nor impede documentation of other trenches being dug concurrently. The sufficiency criterion ruled out hand measurements, while the efficiency criterion ruled out setting up the total station anew each time it was necessary to document a new level. Digital photogrammetry ('photomodeling' in project parlance) seemed to offer a sufficient and efficient solution, inspired by and based in part on methodologies developed for the Gabii Project (Opitz and Nowlin 2012).

An immobile steel box (the "blue box") served to fix the shoring. The blue box in turn anchored the vertically-mobile steel sheeting, periodically lowered in pace with excavation. A series of fixed targets were created on the interior of the blue box using paint pens and clear nail polish, of sufficient size as to be easily visible in photographs. The coordinates of these targets were then measured through the corner openings using a total station in reflectorless mode. Although the blue box is immobile on a macro scale, vertical shifts of up to several centimeters were noted, in particular during the lowering of the steel sheeting. Hence, it was necessary to remeasure the marked points at minimum after every episode of lowering the sheeting, and ideally more frequently, at the beginning of each day.

Using a handheld digital camera, a series of overlapping photographs was taken of both the archaeological surface and at least three of the fixed points on the blue box, including all intervening space. The total number of photographs taken varied with the area and complexity of the surface to be documented, up to a maximum of 100 photos. Although in most instances this far exceeded the number of photographs necessary to produce a sufficient model – even four could adequately model simple surfaces – the additional investment in time was slight enough to err on the side of caution.

Photogrammetrically-derived point cloud of D10 in PhotoScan.

The digital photos were processed using Agisoft PhotoScan. The program creates a point cloud using the principles of structure from motion, matching corresponding pixels between photos and tracking their trajectories to reconstruct camera positions (Hartley and Zisserman 2003). The points serve as vertices in the surface reconstruction of a three-dimensional triangle mesh. The mesh can then be textured with colors from the photos.

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Above L: Assigning coordinates to fixed points visible in a photo; Above R: cropping extraneous surfaces from the model; Below R: the georeferenced decimated model of the archaeological level.

Photogrammetrically-derived models are inherently scaleless; it is necessary to assign the coordinates obtained using the total station to the fixed points visible in the model to scale and orient it. Once the model has been georeferenced using the fixed points, the walls of the trench and any other surfaces extraneous to the desired level can be cropped away. Only the modeled level remains, maintaining its position and topographic data. Among other formats, the surface can be exported as a Digital Elevation Model (DEM). Although a DEM will not preserve the photo texture of the photogrammetric model, PhotoScan can export an orthophoto of the model; the orthophoto can then be draped over the DEM in the GIS if desired.

Modeled stratigraphic units in D10 visualized in ArcSCENE. Above, textured models (black indicates voids left by pumps); right, models assigned arbitrary colors.

The relationships between modeled stratigraphic units can be visualized and measured on a variety of platforms, such as the various components of ArcGIS. The models can also serve as frameworks for hand-characterized drawings; it is critical that computer vision not replace but only assist human vision in archaeological interpretation.

The photomodeling strategy for D10 proved sufficient and efficient, though not without its problems. When it was possible to compare elevation data derived from a model with total station measurements, the values were... Photographing a level took the same or less time than measuring it with a total station, and processing time of completed models was also comparable with that of total station data. However, the (largely automated) creation of the models themselves added to the overall processing time; the most complex models strained the capacity of the laptop computers available in the field and could run to several hours in the worst instances.

The creation of less-detailed models for field use, however, sufficient to use as the basis of hand-characterized drawings, can be done rather more quickly, and the creation of highly-detailed models moved to the post-season when greater processing power is available, as for instance in a university setting.

The presence of small amounts of standing water was sometimes unavoidable. The reflection and refraction produced by even small areas of water has the potential to confuse PhotoScan during point matching. The use of a polarizing filter during photography can reduce some of this reflection, but the benefits must be weighed against the longer exposure times required in an already dark environment and consequent blurriness, especially with a handheld camera.

Visit the Sant'Omobono Project online at:

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